

PECHMANN CONDENSATION OF *p*-ORSELLINIC ACID WITH ETHYL ACETOACETATE. SYNTHESIS OF 7-HYDROXY-4:5-DIMETHYLCOUMARIN.

BY S. M. SETHNA AND R. C. SHAH.

p-Orsellinic acid has been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid yielding 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin-8-carboxylic acid. This on decarboxylation gives 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin which cannot be obtained by the Pechmann condensation of orcinol with ethyl acetoacetate. The decarboxylated product has been assigned the coumarin structure because of its non-identity with 7-hydroxy-2:5-dimethylchromone.

Pechmann condensation of orcinol with malic acid gives 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin (Pechmann and Welsh, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1649), but with ethyl acetoacetate the reaction proceeds abnormally giving 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin (Collie and Chrystall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1804). The condensation of β -resorcylic acid with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid yielding 7-hydroxycoumarin derivative (Shah, *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 717) suggested a possible method for the synthesis of the hitherto unknown 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin by the Pechmann condensation of *p*-orsellinic acid with ethyl acetoacetate and subsequent decarboxylation of the product formed.

p-Orsellinic acid condenses smoothly with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid to give 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin-8-carboxylic acid (I), which on decarboxylation gives 7-hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (II).

The decarboxylated product has been characterised by the preparation of its acetyl and benzoyl derivatives and its methyl ether. It does not give, however, a cinnamic acid derivative and on heating with alkali gives oracetophenone. These facts led the authors first to suspect that the product must be a chromone, *viz.*, 7-hydroxy-2:5-dimethylchromone, which also may be formed, as the formation of a hydroxy-ketone on hydrolysis is believed to be the criterion of a chromone (Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2349).

The decarboxylated product has been found to be different from 7-hydroxy-2:5-dimethylchromone (III), obtained by the Claisen condensation of oracetophenone dimethyl ether with ethyl acetate and subsequent ring-closure of the β -diketone formed. The acetyl and methoxy derivatives of both have also been found to be different. Hence the acid has the coumarin structure (I) and the decarboxylated product is (II).

Experimental evidence has shown so far that a hydroxy-ketone is obtained only on the alkaline hydrolysis of a chromone and not a coumarin

(cf. Baker, *loc. cit.*), but it is quite possible that the coumarin (II) can give oracetophenone (IV) by undergoing hydrolysis along the dotted line (a) after opening of the pyrone ring as shown below :—

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

7-Hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin-8-carboxylic Acid (I).—*p*-Orsellinic acid was prepared by Robertson and Robinson's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2199) by carboxylation of orcinol. On keeping *p*-orsellinic acid with ethyl acetoacetate and concentrated sulphuric acid in the cold for about 30-40 hours the condensation did not take place, *p*-orsellinic acid being recovered unchanged. On heating the above reaction mixture in a boiling water-bath for 2-4 hours, *p*-orsellinic acid was decarboxylated and the product obtained was found to be 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin, which is obtained on Pechmann condensation of orcinol with ethyl acetoacetate. When, however, a temperature of 60-70° was used the condensation was quite facile

To a mixture of *p*-orsellinic acid (10 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (8 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (80 c.c.) was added gradually with shaking. After heating the reaction mixture for 4 hours in a water-bath at 60-70° it was added to cold water. The product obtained was ground up with sodium bicarbonate solution and the solution on acidification gave a product which on crystallisation from rectified spirit gave tiny shining needles (4.5 g.), m. p. 225° (efferv.). It is sparingly soluble in alcohol. It gives a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in alkali with a bluish fluorescence. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 4.5. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ requires C, 61.6; H, 4.3 per cent).

The portion insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution on crystallisation from alcohol gave pale yellow needles, m. p. 253-55°, mixed m. p. with 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin prepared by Pechmann's method from orcinol and ethyl acetoacetate was the same. Pechmann and Cohen (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187) give m. p. 248°.

7-Hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (II).—The above acid (2 g.) was heated in a test-tube in an oil-bath at 230-35° for 10 minutes. The acid melted with effervescence and the solid residue on crystallisation from rectified spirit gave tiny needles (1.3 g.), m. p. 248-50°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 5.3 per cent). Mixed m.p. with 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin was depressed by about 30° and mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-2:5-dimethylchromone was depressed by about 40°. The product gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It dissolves in alkali with a bluish green fluorescence.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual with pyridine and acetic anhydride, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 119-21°. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 5.0. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.1 per cent).

The *benzoyl derivative*, prepared as usual with benzoyl chloride and pyridine, was crystallised from rectified spirit in shining needles, m. p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as usual with sodium hydroxide and dimethyl sulphate, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 117-19°. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 5.7. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent).

Hydrolysis of 7-Hydroxy-4:5-dimethylcoumarin.—The coumarin (0.5 g.) was heated on a boiling water-bath with sodium hydroxide (10%; 15 c.c.) for 5 hours. The solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the product obtained on cooling was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in needles, m.p. 157-59°. Mixed m.p. with oracetophenone prepared by Hoesch's method (*Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1127) was not depressed.

(2':4'-Dimethoxy-6'-methyl)-benzoylacetylmethane.—Dimethyl ether of oracetophenone (6 g.) and ethyl acetate (11 g., approx. 4 mols) were added to pulverised sodium (1.5 g., approx. 2 mols.), the whole being cooled externally by cold water. After the initial vigorous reaction had subsided the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 115-20° for 1 hour. On cooling water was added to the reaction mixture and it was extracted with ether to remove the excess of ethyl acetate and the unreacted dimethylether of oracetophenone. The alkaline solution was acidified with dilute acetic acid when an oil separated which soon solidified.

It crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 74-76°. It gives a reddish violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride (Found : C, 66.3; H, 6.9. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 65.8; H, 7.3 per cent).

The *copper salt*, prepared from the β -diketone and copper acetate, was crystallised from benzene in tiny greenish needles, m.p. 198-200°. [Found : Cu, 11.8. $(C_{13}H_{16}O_4)_2 Cu$ requires Cu, 11.9 per cent]. This salt on decomposition with 10% sulphuric acid gives the original β -diketone back.

7-Methoxy-2:5-dimethylchromone.—To the above β -diketone (2 g.), dissolved in the minimum quantity of acetic anhydride, hydrobromic acid solution (*d* 1.78, 10 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture left overnight. The product obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove any hydroxy-chromone formed. The alkaline solution, however, gave practically nothing on acidification with hydrochloric acid. The alkali-insoluble portion crystallised from rectified spirit as needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 150-52°. (Found : C, 70.8; H, 5.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-2:5-dimethylchromone.—The methyl ether (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 5 c.c.) added gradually. The reaction mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130-40° for 2 hours and then added to sodium bisulphite solution. The product which separated was treated with sodium hydroxide (5%, 15 c.c.). The small quantity of the insoluble portion was found to be the undemethylated methyl ether described above. The alkaline solution was acidified and the product obtained crystallised from rectified spirit in pale yellow glistening needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 253-55°. (Found : C, 69.7; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 5.3 per cent). The product dissolved in sodium hydroxide and in concentrated sulphuric acid with greenish fluorescence.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, crystallised from rectified spirit in long woolly needles, m.p. 125-97°. (Found : C, 67.3; H, 5.2. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.1 per cent).

The styryl derivative could not be obtained either from hydroxy-chromone or its methyl ether and piperonal.

Attempts to hydrolyse the chromone methyl ether by refluxing it with 50% alcoholic caustic potash for 16 hours gave the methyl ether back.